

Addition of Dihalocarbenes to Terpenic Olefins

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Addition of dihalocarbenes to (+) and (-) α -pinenes and camphene have been described. Reactions of dichlorocarbene with (+) and (-) α -pinenes and camphene affords their stable *gem*-dichloro adducts whereas dibromocarbene gives a rearranged monobromo ring expanded olefin and not the expected *gem*-dibromo adduct. The routes and results have been described.

Very little work seems to have been done on the addition of dihalocarbenes to terpenic olefins. Doering and Hoffmann¹ carried out the reactions of dichlorocarbene with α - and β -pinenes. They were able to isolate an adduct (II) of β -pinene (I) and dichlorocarbene but in case of α -pinene no definite compound could be isolated.

We have investigated the addition of dichlorocarbene to the exocyclic double bond of camphene (III). Dichlorocarbene for this reaction was generated by the action of potassium *t*-butoxide and chloroform in nonprotic media. The reaction

mixture on processing afforded 2, 2-dimethyl norbornane spiro-(2', 2'-dichloro-cyclopropane) (IV) in 10% yield. This adduct will favour to have an

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exo-stereochemistry as the bridge methylene protons and the two chlorine atoms (at C-2) will have steric hindrance for the *endo*-structure.

The following evidence supports the adduct formation at the exocyclic double bond: The saturated character of the adduct was indicated by its complete inertness towards tetranitromethane, bromine in chloroform and aqueous potassium permanganate solutions and also by IR spectra which does not show any absorption in the 1620-1680 cm^{-1} region. Other absorption bands in IR (thin film) appeared at 2990, 1470 ($-\text{CH}_2$), 1047, 1020 (cyclopropane ring), 900, 877 (cyclohexane and cyclobutane rings), 806 and 757 (C-Cl) cm^{-1} . NMR (in carbontetrachloride) has no signal for any unsaturated proton in the range $\sim 4.7\tau$. However, it depicts several saturated methyl and methylene protons at 8.9, 8.78, 8.5, 8.1 and 8.0 τ .

We have carefully reinvestigated the reactions of dichlorocarbene with (+) and (-) α -pinenes (VA and VB) separately and have isolated (+) and (-)-2, 8, 8-trimethyl-3, 3-dichlorotricyclo [4.1.1.0^{2,7}] octane (VIA and VIB) respectively in crystalline form. It would be reasonable to assume that both *cis*- and *trans*- conformations^a of α -pinene (V) may exist in equilibrium, but the adduct (VI) would prefer to have a *trans*-pinene ring conformation. This may be accounted on the basis of high steric interaction between *gem*-dichloro group (at C-3) and *gem*-dimethyl (at C-8) in the *cis*-conformation; however this interaction is minimized in the *trans*-structure where the *gem*-dichloro group is far apart from the *gem*-dimethyl group of the bridge.

The adducts have been assigned structures (VI A) and (VI B) on the following grounds:

Bromine in carbon tetrachloride, aqueous alkaline potassium permanganate solutions and tetranitromethane remained unaffected showing their saturated character. Their IR spectra are superimposable and have no absorption bands in the 1680-1620 cm^{-1} region. Presence of cyclopropane ring has been supported by a strong absorption at 1010 cm^{-1} , other bands appeared at 1460, 1375, 1260, 980, 975, and 950 cm^{-1} . NMR shows no signal for unsaturated proton ($\sim 4.7\tau$), methyl

protons appear at 8.48, 8.59, and 8.9T and other saturated protons at 7.47, 7.7 and 7.9T.

However, when dibromocarbene was allowed to react with (+) α -pinene, the *gem*-dibromo cyclopropyl adduct (VII) could not be isolated under experimental conditions, it immediately underwent dehydrobromination to afford the rearranged olefinic product. This could have either structure (VIII A) or (VIII B). On the basis of following evidence we have assigned the structure for this product as 2, 8, 8-trimethyl-3-bromo-bicyclo [4.1.1] oct-2-ene (VIII B).

(1) The product showed unsaturation towards bromine in carbon tetrachloride and aqueous alkaline potassium permanganate solutions. It also gave an orange

red colour with tetranitromethane. (2) IR (thin film) showed the presence of a sharp band at 1615 cm^{-1} (tetrasubstituted double bond), 2941 (C-H), 1460 , 952 , 909 (cyclobutane ring), 1379 , 1307 , 1250 , 1150 , and 730 (C-Br) cm^{-1} . (3) Structure (VIII A) must show an olefinic proton in its NMR, but NMR of the reaction product does not show signal for any unsaturated proton ($\sim 4.7T$ region). Thus structure (VIII A) was eliminated. This observation is quite in agreement with the other most probable structure (VIII B). The sharp singlets at 8.9, 8.72, 8.64, 8.37 and 8.2T appear due to the protons of methyl groups. The remaining signals at 8.0 and 7.68T are due to other saturated protons in the molecule.

While this work was in progress, similar observations have been reported

simultaneously from five laboratories⁸⁻⁷ in respect of the addition of dichlorocarbene and dibromocarbene to norbornylene (IX).

The dehydrobromination step for the formation of (VIII B) is supported by few similar examples which are on record in the literature. Cyclopentadiene reacts with dichlorocarbene to yield dichloro adduct (X) which undergoes dehydrohalogenation to afford chlorobenzene⁸.

However, cycloheptatriene under similar reaction conditions affords 1-chlorobenzocyclobutane⁹ (XI).

Another interesting example of dehydrohalogenation is the thermal treatment of 2-oxa-7,7-dichloronorcarane¹⁰ (XII) which undergoes ring expansion.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Solvents and material :—B. D. H. chloroform and bromoform were washed 5 to 6 times with water, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and finally distilled. Hexane, pentane and petroleum ether (40°-60°) were completely freed from olefinic impurities and distilled over sodium before use. Anhydrous potassium *t*-butoxide was freshly prepared for each experiment as described by Doering et al.¹.

Reaction of chloroform, potassium *t*-butoxide and camphene :—The reaction was carried out in a three necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser, drying tube, mercury sealed stirrer, and a dropping funnel. Chloroform (27 g, 0.23 mole) was added from the dropping funnel (over a period of 4 hr) to a constantly stirring slurry of potassium *t*-butoxide (from 15 g. potassium) and camphene (30 g., 0.23 mole) in olefin free petroleum ether (500 ml) at -10°. After complete addition of chloroform the mixture was further stirred for 2 hr. at 0°. It was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 36 hr. and then poured into water (500 ml), the aqueous layer was extracted with petroleum ether. The combined organic layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Recovery of the solvent gave a dark brown liquid which on distillation yielded camphene (26.6 g., 85%) and a colourless liquid at 80-85°/0.5mm (2.5 g., 8-10%). The latter fraction was redistilled to yield a TLC pure sample (solvent system: ethylacetate and benzene :: 1:25, v/v) of 2, 2-dimethyl norbornane spiro-(2' 2'-dichlorocyclopropane) (IV). (Found C, 59.99; H, 7.60; Cl, 32.30. C₁₁H₁₆Cl₂ requires C, 60.29; H, 7.4; Cl, 32.40%). It did not decolorize either bromine solution in carbontetrachloride or alkaline potassium permanganate, and also it did not give any colour reaction with tetranitromethane.

Reaction of chloroform, potassium *t*-butoxide and (+) α -pinene : In a three necked flask equipped with a dropping funnel, mercury sealed stirrer, reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube, anhydrous potassium *t*-butoxide (from 11g. potassium metal) was covered with olefin free hexane (150 ml) and then cooled to -10°, α -pinene (25 g., 0.18 mole) dissolved in hexane (100 ml) was added to the cooled butoxide suspension. The cooled butoxide- α -pinene slurry was treated dropwise with chloroform (22 g., 0.18 mole, diluted with 50 ml hexane) with constant stirring. The addition of chloroform was extended over 1.5 hr. After complete addition of chloroform the mixture was stirred for 1 hr more at ~-10°. It was left for 12 hr. in an ice bath and then poured into water (500 ml). The hexane layer was separated and again washed with water (3 x 50 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and hexane recovered under diminished pressure on a waterbath (temperature 40-50°). The reddish brown liquid was poured on a watch glass and scratching it for a long time with a glass rod afforded needle shaped crystalline mass. Repeated crystallizations with methanol gave white needles (m.p. 65-66°) of 2, 8, 8-trimethyl-3, 3-dichloro tricyclo [4.1.1.0^{3,4}] octane (VI A). During crystallizations heating of this substance above its m.p. was avoided because the compound is very sensitive to heat and decomposes very soon. Long exposure

* All melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

to light also brings about the decomposition. $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 83.25^\circ$ (in chloroform). Found : C, 59.97 ; H, 7.29 ; Cl, 32.31. $C_{11}H_{16}Cl_2$ requires C, 60.30 ; H, 7.40 ; Cl, 32.40%. The adduct did not decolourize bromine in carbontetrachloride and alkaline potassium permanganate solutions. It gave no colouration with tetranitromethane.

Reaction of chloroform, potassium t-butoxide and (-) α -pinene : The reaction was carried out exactly in the manner as described for (+) α -pinene and dichlorocarbene. The reaction mixture afforded white needles (m.p. 65-66°) of (-) 2, 8, 8-trimethyl-3, 3-dichloro tricyclo [4.1.1.0^{2,4}] octane (VIB). $[\alpha]_D^{30} - 83.19^\circ$ (in chloroform). (Found : C, 60.10 ; H, 7.37 ; Cl, 32.3. $C_{11}H_{16}Cl_2$ requires C, 60.3 ; H, 7.4 ; Cl, 32.4%). Bromine in carbontetrachloride, alkaline potassium permanganate and tetranitromethane solutions remained unaffected. Its IR spectra (in nujol mull) overlap with the spectra obtained for the -dichloro adduct of (+) α -pinene.

Reaction of bromoform, potassium t-butoxide and (+) α -pinene : Anhydrous potassium t-butoxide from (12 g. potassium metal) was placed in a three necked round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser, a mercury sealed stirrer, a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube. The flask was cooled to -5° in a freezing mixture bath and petroleum ether (130 ml, olefin free) was added to it. The solution was stirred and cooled. α -pinene (27 g., 0.22 mole) diluted with petroleum ether (100 ml) was then added in one lot. The α -pinene-butoxide slurry was again cooled to -5° to -10°. Bromoform (42.0 g., 0.22 mole) dissolved in petroleum ether (75 ml) was added to the reaction mixture with constant stirring. The addition period of bromoform was extended over to 2 hr. and the maximum temperature was maintained to -5° during the reaction period. After complete addition of bromoform the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 hr more in ice bath and then left for 24 hr. at room temperature. It was again stirred for 1 hr at room temperature and then poured into water (500 ml). The organic layer was separated, thoroughly washed with additional portions of water, and finally dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent afforded a reddish brown liquid which was fractionally distilled to yield unreacted α -pinene (55-57°/4.0 mm) and 2, 8, 8, trimethyl-3-bromo bicyclo [4.1.1] oct-2-ene (VIIB) (90-94°/6.0 mm). (Found : C, 57.98 ; H, 6.93 ; Br, 35.25. $C_{11}H_{16}Br$ requires C, 57.9 ; H, 7.0 ; Br, 35.10%). It gave an orange red colouration with tetranitromethane and also decolourized bromine in carbontetrachloride and alkaline potassium permanganate solutions.

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